

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Critical Analysis of Energy Consumption and Its Impact on Countries Economic Growth: An empirical analysis base on Countries income level

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Abstract

Energy is a very important and key factor for developing countries like China, India, and Pakistan have a growth rate of population is very high. In today's changing world scenario of Petroleum price high, that increasing the gap between demand and supply of energy in the World. Energy shortage is a test case for governments due to the high demand for energy due to rising commercial need, consumption, and industrialization. Current economic and energy crisis scenarios force me to work on those issues. An objective of the study is to test the long-run connection between energy consumption and economic progress from 1971 to 2021. This study adopts the Unit Root Test for stationary, Cointegrating equation and Vector Error Correction used for short-run/long-run relationship; Granger Causality test used for find-out the causal association, and Ordinary least square to examine the impact between energy sources and economic progress. The study result shows Oil, Gas and Electricity are equally important short run/long run, while the Coal log-run is more than in the short-run. The energy consumption to economic growth has a unidirectional causality, indicating energy is a factor that affects country growth. Regression results also confirm that energy significance on top for economic growth, Energy Sources; Gas and Electricity were useful but energy source Oil getting more attention in past decades. Currently, high-cost sources of energy, i.e. up Oil prices, this study suggest the alternate energy source nuclear, wind and solar to ensure low-cost energy generation to economic growth.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Resource of Energy, Energy Consumption, Causal Relationship.

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1.Introduction

1.1Research Background

Energy is a key element for a country and the main factor for the economy; the Energy field plays a critical role in Countries Growth, mostly the manufacturing sector. An optimistic long-run cointegrated association between actual Gross Domestic Product and energy consumption. There is no causality between short and long-run, unidirectional causality between energy consumption and economic growth. It shows energy utilization deduction does not affect G.D.P. in the short run but in the long run (C. C. Lee & C-P Chang, 2008). Compared to other

World Pakistan has an inverse relationship in the technology sector. But in the United States, no association was found between energy utilization and gross domestic product, which effectively increased employment and economy. McKinnon and Shaw (1973) examine the relations among energy consumption and countries growth. Energy has to attain a high level of the central position of economic progress.

Alam and But (2002), co-integration and unidirectional causality founded among the energy utilization and country growth.